

ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH NUMERALS

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Annotation: *This article provides information on the use of numerals and its analysis. There is also information about the fractions and quantitative representations of numbers.*

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The most characteristic feature of a numeral as a part of speech is its number value.

The numeral name is a part of speech that denotes an abstract number (number), as well as the order of objects when counting them: one, two, ten; one second, three fourth; two, three, five; first, second, tenth.

The quantitative value can be transmitted not only by numbers, but also by words from other parts of speech: three, five, one hundred; triple, tenfold. However, the abstract meaning of quantity (number) is inherent in one numeral. The abstraction of the quantitative semantics of numerals is manifested in the following:

1. Numerals can denote quantity (number) without any connection to any specific subject and are indicated by numbers on the letter:

$$2 + 2=4, 2 \times 2=4, 2: 2 = 1, 2 - 2=0.$$

2. The quantitative (numerical) meaning of numerals is not complicated by other values. Three, triple, and triple are different parts of speech, since they express quantitative meaning differently. Troika is a noun, because it is always associated with the subject: troika is the name of a mark (get a troika); the name of a men's suit consisting of three parts (sew a troika); the name of a playing card (troika of diamonds); the name of a three-person commission (emergency troika). Triple is a verb, because it always refers to an action as a process: triple - increase by three times. Only three is a numeral, because it expresses a quantity (number) and nothing else.

Grammatical features of numerals are not as uniform and indicative as the semantics of the considered part of speech. The words one, three, and one thousand are all numbers in terms of their semantics. But in morphological terms,

they are not uniform: one varies by gender (one house, one room, one window); three does not have the category of gender; a thousand - the word gen. gender and does not change by gender. Grammatical heterogeneity of numerals determines the description of their grammatical features within a particular category of numerals.

By value, all numerals are divided into quantitative, indefinite-quantitative, ordinal, and collective ones.

Numerals that express an abstract quantity (number) are called quantitative.

Quantitative numerals are divided into numerals that name integers or the number of whole objects (two, three, ten), and numerals that name parts of integers or the number of parts of objects - fractional (one and a half, one-second, two-thirds). Quantitative numerals denote an exact, definite number of items (two tables, five houses, one hundred roads, etc.).

Indefinite-quantitative numerals denote an indefinite number of objects (persons) or substances: a lot, a little, a little (a lot of tables, debts, roads, etc.).

Ordinal numbers are numbers that indicate the order of items when they are counted: first, second, fifth, hundredth, one hundred and tenth.

Collective numbers are numbers that refer to the number of units that form a set of objects: two, three, five, etc.

Quantitative numerals are the main category, since: 1) they make possible the formation and functioning of other semantic categories; 2) they have specific grammatical features, which is not so typical for other numerals.

Structural digits of numerals

By structure, numerals can be non-derived, or simple, and derived.

There are few non-derived (simple) numerals: quantitative numbers of the first ten (one, two, three, ten) and numerals of forty, one hundred, and one thousand. In the modern language, simple numbers can be attributed to one and a half (fractional), million, billion (they are now not divided into morphemes).

Derived numerals combine two groups: complex and compound numerals.

Complex numbers are one-word numerals formed from simple ones (eleven, twenty, fifty, two hundred, five hundred, eleven, fiftieth, etc.). From quantitative numerals, these are the names of units of the second ten, tens, and hundreds.

The names of units of the second ten come from combinations of the names of units of the first ten with the preposition *na* and the numeral ten in the local (prepositional) case: eleven out of one in ten ("one unit over ten"); twelve out of two in ten, and so on. As a result of phonetic changes, the numeral ten with the preposition *on* turned into-twelve. Similar transformations occurred in the

numerals twenty, thirty, which go back to the combinations of the numerals two, three and the numeral ten in the nominative case of the dual and plural (ten). Two hundred, three hundred became twenty, thirty.

The numerals fifty, sixty, seventy, and eighty are formed from combining the names of units and the numeral ten in the genitive plural. The origin of the numeral ninety is not exactly established.

The numeral two hundred is a fusion of the numerals two and one hundred (in the nominative case of the dual number). The numerals three hundred, four hundred go back to the Old English combinations of the numerals three, four and the numeral hundred (nominative plural of one hundred). The numerals five hundred, six hundred, seven hundred, eight hundred, nine hundred are derived from the combinations five, six, seven, eight, nine and the numeral one hundred in the genitive plural (sot).

Compound numbers are non-word numerals that were formed by juxtaposing (composing) simple and complex numbers (twenty-one, one hundred and thirty-seven, one thousand five hundred and eighty-five, twenty-one, one hundred and thirty-seven). Composite numbers are a productive group, whereas complex numbers in the modern language are not supplemented with new formations. By combining a few simple and complex numbers, we can denote any large or small number (number).

Grammatical features of quantitative numerals

Quantitative numerals are the most peculiar category in grammatical terms. Morphologically, they are characterized by the absence of the gender category in most words, and syntactically-by a special compatibility with nouns.

Fractional numbers

Fractional numbers are called parts of integers, the number of parts of whole objects, or a collection of objects. The numerator is a quantitative number, and the denominator is an ordinal number. If the numerator is the numeral one or a composite numeral with the final component one, then the ordinal numeral in the denominator has the form of the feminine singular of the nominative case: one fifth, twenty-one hundredths. In all other fractional numerals, the ordinal number is in the genitive plural form: two-fifths, twenty-hundredths. In indirect cases, the numerator and denominator agree: one-fifth, two-fifths, twenty-one hundredths.

Fractional numbers require the noun to be set in the genitive case: one-sixth of the earth, three-tenths of vegetables. Fractional numerals, in contrast to quantitative ones, can be combined with collective and real nouns (three-fifths of youth, three-fifths of butter), naming the number of parts of any set of objects

(persons) or substances. In combination with nouns denoting items that can be counted (tree, house, city, etc.), fractional numbers can indicate either the number of parts of one item, or the number of parts of the entire set of these items: one second of a tree, one second of trees. In the first case, the noun is in the genitive singular, and in the second-in the genitive plural.

Fractional numbers are also one and a half (masculine and neuter), one and a half (feminine), and one and a half hundred. These numbers have some special features.

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